

A one-stop portal

Our proposition

The power of working together

This is us

6 partners from 4 EU countries have joined forces to bridge the gap between cutting-edge AI, healthcare expertise in pediatric oncology, impact creation and community building

A crowdsourced ecosystem to fight childhood cancer

eu4child

Stay in touch!

www.eu4child.eu

@eu4child

/eu4child

EU4CHILD receives funding from the European Union's Call for Pilot Projects and Preparatory Actions (PPPA) under Grant Agreement No. 101018783

Why Childhood Cancer?

The facts

Many paediatric cancers have a genetically distinct component from their adult counterparts, highlighting the need for **childhood-specific genomic studies, datasets and therapeutic strategies**

Specificity is the mark

Early detection is key

Young survivors deserve better

Bringing together healthcare professionals, young cancer patients and AI experts

We seek to connect **key European stakeholders** in Childhood Cancer by means of **eXplainable AI** to facilitate the interaction and cooperation of top actors among them

A multidisciplinary roadmap to fight Childhood Cancer

A multi-perspective (ethical, privacy, governance, medical-based, AI specialists, IT, infrastructure and industry) State-of-the-Art, complemented by a **roadmap** and **guidelines** on the **mechanisms and tools** to implement the ecosystem

Artificial Intelligence to improve cancer care

Our tools

EU4CHILD will provide **top-quality, evidence-based AI services** to accelerate the **diagnosis, prognosis and treatment** of children with cancer

AI
medical
imaging

Natural
Language
Processing

Deep
Neural
Networks

Breaking down health data silos

Our ambition

We will fight the reluctance to share health-related data through solid **ethics** and **data governance**

Fostering
Open Innovation

Enabling
interoperability

Top AI
performance
and quality

A sound data
strategy

A single access point to boost knowledge exchange and collaboration opportunities

EU4CHILD will build a **one-stop portal** to host and curate a **EU-wide knowledge base** for childhood cancer, providing **insights** on the disease and liaising **future opportunities** for collaboration